

THE ROLE OF DERIVATION AND ABBREVIATION IN WORD FORMATION IN RECENT YEARS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6709683>

Abstract. *The process of formation of new units occurs in accordance with the morphological processes existing in the language. Among the morphological devices operating in the French language, one can indicate derivation and abbreviation. Linguistic studies are included in this article because derivation is one of the main sources for the creation of words and the updating of technical languages, as well as the francization of terms from other languages. For our study, we turned to the studies of various linguists, such as Sablirol, Espersen, Vinogradov, Maslova, and others. Following our deepening, we made a linguistic and cultural analysis of these neologisms, such as diachronic, semantic analysis, etc. In the course of our analysis, we saw that the derivation consists of two types of formation, such as a suffix and a prefix. In the content of the article, we tried to show the suffixes and prefixes most commonly used in French.*

Key words: *derivation, abbreviation, suffix and prefix, polysemy, diachronic analysis, semantic neologisms, semantic restriction, semantic expansion, cultural connotations.*

INTRODUCTION

Each language enriches thanks to the dramatic transformation of society, thanks to new technology and scientific innovations. To express these changes, new words are introduced into the language. The introduction of the new word into the language can be through inward and outward movements like composition and derivation, borrowings from another language, layers, or through tropes as well.

At the same time, in the 21st century, in addition to borrowing, the neology is enriched with the help of morphological processes. The fabrication process of new units unfolds according to the morphologic processes in the language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Among the morphological processes in force in French, we can cite the derivation and the abbreviation.

By doing the grammatical analysis of new words of the Petit Larousse of 2001, 2015, 2016, 2017, we count that about 164 derived words, under them the 102 are the nouns, 29 words are the verbs and 35 words are the adjectives.

If we group by ratio of formation of derived words, 104 words formed by suffixes, on the other hand this figure, 60 words formed by prefixes.

The most frequent suffixes are "-isme", "-iste", "-tion" according to dictionaries of the 4 years, which show words keeping cultural traits. For instance,

- a) The words formed by “-isme”, “-iste” of the 2020: antispécisme, cyberdihadisme ou cyberjihadisme, locavorisme, narcobanditisme, spécisme, suprémacisme, survivalisme, néosurvivalisme, assimilationniste, assimilationnisme, muraliste, muralisme, transhumaniste, transhumanisme, artiste, cyberdihadiste, cosmologiste, jobiste ;
- b) The words formed by “-isme”, “-iste” of 2019 : flexitarisme, sans-abrisme, hacktivisme, dégagisme, animalisme, animaliste, hacktiviste, néocriticiste, ;

- c) The words formed by “-isme”, “-iste” of 2018 : droit-de-l’hommeisme, européenisme, européeniste, européisme, européiste, djihadisme, céiste, polyphoniste ;
- d) The words formed by “-isme”, “-iste” of 2017 : complotisme, néokeynésianisme, thalassotropisme, transhumanisme ; complotiste ;
- e) The words formed by “-isme”, “-iste” of 2016 : écopatrolisme, mormonisme, social-libéralisme, crudivorisme, européiste ;
- f) The words formed by “-isme”, “-iste” of 2015 : véganisme, nativisme ;
- g) The words formed by “-isme”, “-iste” of 2001 : agrochimiste, amérindianisme, annexionnisme, panurgisme.

The prefix, after the suffix, forms many words, rather the prefixes "dé-" and "micro-", "anti-" are encountered in the Larousse dictionary from 2001 to 2020. For example :

- a) The words formed by “dé-” and “anti-” of the 2017: *déclinisme, défaçade, dézipper ; antisystème, antitumoral ;*
- b) The words formed by “dé-” and “anti-”, “micro-” of the 2016 : *dédiaboliser, dédiabolisation, dézonage ; antépisode, microfiction ;*
- c) The words formed by “micro-” of the 2015 : *microbiote, micropaiement, microtransaction ;*
- d) The words formed by “dé-” and “micro-” of the du 2001 : *déambulateur, microbrasserie.*

There are still neologisms that take the suffix and the prefix at the same time:

1. the formation of the name *microbrasserie*, by adding the prefix **micro** – to the name *brasserie* the word *brasserie* by adding the suffix **-erie** to the verb "brasser";
2. the formation of the noun *dédiabolisation*, by adding the suffix **-ation** to the verb *dédiaboliser*, the verb *dédiaboliser* by adding the prefix **dé** – to the other verb *diaboliser*;
3. the formation of the noun *insaisissabilité* is formed with the suffix *insaisissable* + **ité**, the adjective *insaisissable* by the addition of the prefix **in-saisissable**, the adjective *saisissable* is by the verb *saisir*+ the suffix *-able* etc...

Sometimes by a radical we form some words: **spéc-** *spéciste, spécisme, antisécisme ; mondial-* *antimondialisation, antimondialiste ; altermondialisation, altermondialisme, altermondialiste ; installer-* *désinstallation, désinstaller.*

RESULTS

We have already counted that out of the 603 words in 22 words are the new abbreviations. Of the 22 words, 11 are acronyms and the remainder are truncations.

There are several methodes to abbreviate groupes of words, the most courante are a siglaison and acronym, troncation.

Siglaison consiste to take the initials of several words and accole them together. For example: PAF ou P.A.F. RMA or R.M.A. R'N'B.

The same acronyme can have many and very deffent meanings depending on the era and the country. for exemple a humoristic or denonciative fonction.

For example: ADM can designate: Aéroports de Montréal ou Autoroutes du Maroc.

The acronym ALD also has some meaning: *Affection de longue durée*- the abbreviation in medicine; Automobiles Louis Descartes – a former French racing team.

A practical and economical linguistic means, the siglaison process is also part of the linguistic mechanisms of neological creation because the reduced form has an autonomous status in relation to the basic form. It is very common in neonymy because each language tends to abbreviate part of its lexicon, either by abbreviation or by truncation.

DISCUSSION

During our research on abbreviated neologisms, we had questions about whether they have cultural values and if so which ones. In our opinion, acronyms and acronyms do not have cultural connotations, because they are only abbreviated words to facilitate the use of sentences and they are in addition to scientific words. For example, the R.E.P. (*Réseau d'éducation prioritaire* acronym - Priority Education Network) - in France, an area where educational action is reinforced to fight against school failure.

It is an educational term, which replaced ZEP in 2015. If we are innovating in the field of education, it is doubtful not to replace this term with another one. The truncation can express the realities of society. The train-tram is a tram train capable of running both on lines located on the road, in town, and on regional railway lines, on the outskirts. A televangelist is a preacher who hosts evangelistic television programs.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, derivation is a process of enrichment of the language very used inside the language, and especially the suffixes form the new words by adding to the existing words or the borrowings. By doing the analysis we saw that the suffixes and the prefixes rather form the nouns and the adjectives, the majority of the prefixes are of Latin and Greek origin like *micro-*, *anti-*, *co-*, *dé-* etc.

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